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“From Individual Lamentation to Universal Empathy: The Elegy in the English Literature”

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Abstract: Verse is one of the oldest forms of literature. This form is closest to human hearts due to its rhythmic pattern. It is easy to remember for long years. It has its origin from the oral tradition. Poetry has several genres like epic, lyric, ballad, sonnet, dramatic monologue, elegy etc. Elegy is one of the vital genres of poetry. There are several elegiac pieces of poetry. Here in this paper there will be a detailed analysis of some of the significant elegies of English Literature. Elegies are reflective pieces of literature which often deal with some loss, death, mortality, heartache etc. The tone is automatically gloomy and melancholic where the poet is mourning for some irreparable loss. According to M.H. Abrams Elegy is -**In Greek and Roman times, “elegy” denoted any poem written in elegiac meter (alternating hexameter and pentameter lines).** Subject matter of these poems is grave and very serious. In Old English Literature there are some marvelous elegies like The Sea farer, The Wanderer, The Wife’s Lament; Deor’s Lament etc. all these literary pieces have enriched English Literature and have aided this literary genre to reach its improvement and perfection. Elegiac poetry through its profound subject matter not only lightens the grief and emotional baggage of the poets but also touches the hearts of the readers worldwide. It makes personal grief universal. There lies the acceptance of Literature as it establishes that human emotion is universal irrespective caste, class, gender and geographical borders. The close reading of the poems and the interpretative textual analysis accompanied with the historical contexts enrich the methodological aspect of this research study. The literature review focuses mostly on the

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individual elegies of the concerning era and provide detailed elaboration and close analysis of the texts. The psychological, archetypal, ecocritical, fundamental elegiac and anti –elegy theoretical approaches help in the effective comprehension of the elegies.

Key Words: elegy, death, loss, lament, mourn, grave, pastoral, beloved, console, personal, universal, emotional, acceptance, spiritual, mundane, empathy

Introduction: Elegy is the sophisticated response of humans beings mostly after the massive and irrevocable loss of their near and dear ones or the loss of something very essential to them. With the advancement of time this poetic form has gone through several transformations to elevate its standard. Through the dignified use of elegiac tone individual mourning achieves universal empathetic response thus globalizing precious humane emotions. In the Renaissance period pastoral elegy was a classical form to pay homage to a deceased person. Usually Elegy proceeds through following three major steps- **Lamentation**- where the poet expresses his profound sorrow for the deceased person, **Admiration**- in this middle section of the poem the poet glorifies the unique qualities of the unworldly person, his memories or his special position in the poet’s heart and in his life. His contributions, his significant works in his lifetime etc. are cited generally. **Consolation**- The elegy mostly concludes with acceptance of the universal truth, mortality and the ultimate departure of the soul from the mundane world to the celestial domain. The poet prays for the peaceful existence of the departed soul in the afterlife and consoles himself and his readers with this consideration that where mortality ends there spiritual immortality and eternity of the soul begins.

Methodology: This research undergoes qualitative textual analysis and close reading of all the texts. The interpretative, comparative, descriptive- analytical approaches help to intensely grasp the unique features of these elegies. The interdisciplinary research methodology integrating psychological, archetypal, ecocritical, fundamental elegiac and anti –elegy theories delve deep into the textual analysis. The secondary sources like the scholarly and analytical writings, articles provide deeper insight of the momentous subject matters of the poems.

Literature Review:

- **OLD English Elegies: The Wanderer, The Seafarer, The Wife's Lament** are the three significant elegies of Old English. These three elegies are in the Exeter book. The themes of these poems are loss, exile, ruin and journey. These poems express grief, helplessness and loneliness.
- **Deor’s Lament:** is another excellent example of Old English elegy. Here the scop or the bard is lamenting over his sudden misfortune. He has been replaced by a fellow poet, his rival and has lost his patronizer’s favor. Though initially it hurts him extremely but instead of getting depressed he is motivating himself thoroughly that failure is a natural incident which is temporary but it can be reverted with constant endeavor, passion and indomitable spirit. He is using a refrain to enhance his energy **“That passed away; this also may”** or

sometimes translated as "**that passed over, so may this**". Here in this elegiac work some Germanic legends like Weland, Theodoric, Ermanaric are mentioned. The poet here compares his own distressful condition with these legendary figures and has strengthened his moral power effectively. He consoles himself that if they can overcome their worst time with patience, perseverance and hard work, he can also transform his temporary disappointment with everlasting success by his dedication to his work. This elegy is also in the Exeter Book.

Weland endured the agony of exile:
an indomitable smith wracked by grief.
He suffered countless sorrows;
indeed, such sorrows were his bosom companions
in that frozen island dungeon
where Nithad fettered him:
so many strong-but-supple sinew-bands
binding the better man.
That passed away; this also may.

- **Lycidas(1637):John Milton-** John Milton is a gigantic literary figure in English literature. He was a prolific writer and even his blindness could not stop him from contributing immeasurably in English Literature. He has enriched English Literature with his enormous talent and massive and skillful writing. His indomitable spirit has contributed a lot to the global prestige and grand stature of this literature. Lycidas is a pastoral elegy which he has written after the sudden demise of his Cambridge friend, Edward King. He had unfortunately drowned in the Irish Sea. Here in this poem Milton appreciates the selflessness of his friend which is rarely seen in the clergies. He accuses God for his friend's untimely death. He was a man with enormous potential but due to this sudden death his talents could not flourish. Milton himself was a novice writer that time so he with little poetical experience had gathered courage to tribute his friend. They met in the "self-same hill" Christ's College of Cambridge. Like the accidental untimely death of the King the poet- shepherd's verse is also unripe, inexperienced-

Yet once more, O ye laurels, and once more
Ye myrtles brown, with ivy never sere,
I come to pluck your berries harsh and crude,
And with forc'd fingers rude
Shatter your leaves before the mellowing year.

The poet here follows the pastoral form of poetry to mourn the death of his beloved friend. Through this conventional classical mode of poetry he aptly expresses his sorrow and sudden tragedy with the simplicity of the pastoral setting in the backdrop. The vivacity and vitality of nature are expressed vividly through his expert writing skill. In this elegy the poet bewails the

futility of human toil and the transience of human existence. Milton in this elegy has fearlessly condemned the unethical practices of the clergies, "**corrupted clergy,**" the "**blind mouths**" (119), their corruption and extreme selfishness which prove fatal for the innocent public. Though starts with grief, lamentation it ultimately chooses Christian faith of the afterlife. It may be Lycidas has to experience premature worldly departure but it helps him to enter in the eternal spiritual realm where he attains peace and immortality.

The elegy though a masterpiece in itself but the great 18th c. literary critic Dr. Samuel Johnson has sharply criticized the poem that- **It is not to be considered as the effusion of real passion; for passion runs not after remote allusions and obscure opinions. Passion plucks no berries from the myrtle and ivy, nor calls upon Arethuse and Mincius, nor tells of rough satyrs and fauns with cloven heel. Where there is leisure for fiction there is little grief.** In the "Life of Milton" (1779), Dr. Johnson, has disparaged "Lycidas" due to "its inherent improbability". Johnson disagrees with the combination of mythology and pastoralism in the elegiac poems.

- **Elegy Written in a Country Churchyard (1751): Thomas Gray-** This elegy is a masterpiece in English Literature. The poem was popularized by Thomas Gray's friend, Horace Walpole. This elegy though partly written as a tribute to Richard West's death in 1742 but it is an elegy to Death itself. Gray's Elegy is a grave contemplation on Death. This elegy is at once personal and universal. It has gained huge popularity and cordial acceptance all over the world for its equalization of human beings irrespective of their class, creed, economic condition and social status. This great poem has achieved immense recognition and is translated in multiple languages. This elegy pays homage to each and every human being and there lies its acceptance and grand achievement. This unique literary piece is close to the heart of everyone. The tone of the poem is thoroughly philosophical, empathetic and melancholic.

The boast of heraldry, the pomp of pow'r,
And all that beauty, all that wealth e'er gave,
Awaits alike th' inevitable hour.
The paths of glory lead but to the grave.

Like the rich successful people the poor humble people should attain remembrances after their death. The humble villagers –the poor forefathers of the village may have lived a quiet, simple and peaceful life in contrast with the luxurious, busy and eventful lives of the ambitious human beings but these people should also be honored after their death. They may not strive for name, fame and money but they have not indulged in any kind of mischievous activities for their own selfish pursuit. They have deliberately chosen contentment rather than overarching ambition, they want a simple rustic life rather than hectic urbane existence. Simplicity and innocence are preferred rather than unnecessary complication.

Far from the madding crowd's ignoble strife,
Their sober wishes never learn'd to stray;
Along the cool sequester'd vale of life
They kept the noiseless tenor of their way.

Yet ev'n these bones from insult to protect,
Some frail memorial still erected nigh,
With uncouth rhymes and shapeless sculpture deck'd,
Implores the passing tribute of a sigh.

These poor villagers may have possessed unique qualities and geniuses but these talents have not flourished due to lack of resources and facilities.

Full many a gem of purest ray serene,
The dark unfathom'd caves of ocean bear:
Full many a flow'r is born to blush unseen,
And waste its sweetness on the desert air.

In the final section of the poem Gray has written his own epitaph to tribute his own impending death. He projects himself as a humble and simple man. It may be that he has not done something great in his life but whatever he has done is with utmost sincerity and genuineness. He was never a very fortunate man in his lifetime as melancholy always accompanied him.

Here rests his head upon the lap of Earth
A youth to Fortune and to Fame unknown.
Fair Science frown'd not on his humble birth,
And Melancholy mark'd him for her own.

- **Adonais(1821): Percy Bysshe Shelley** – Adonais is another brilliant elegy in English Literature. Like Milton's Lycidas this poem is also a pastoral elegy. The "least imperfect" poem is consisting of 55 Spenserian stanzas where the first eight lines are written in Iambic pentameter and the last 9th line is of iambic hexameter with the ababbcbcc rhyming scheme. Here in this poem Shelley has closely followed Milton's style of elegy writing. Adonais also has juxtaposed pastoralism with mythology. Shelley has written this elegy immediately after the death of his beloved friend, John Keats. The elegy laments the premature death of the genius romantic poet Keats whom he met through their mutual friend, Leigh Hunt.

But now, thy youngest, dearest one, has perish'd,
The nursling of thy widowhood, who grew,
Like a pale flower by some sad maiden cherish'd,

And fed with true-love tears, instead of dew;

In this elegy the poet invokes the muse Urania, Adonais's mother to mourn the death of the unparallel spirit. Adonais is the Greek God of beauty, youth and reincarnation. As Keats was always fond of aesthetics and natural beauty so he is called Adonais by his admirer friend, Shelley.

Shelley is of this view that extreme pessimistic criticisms and reviews have enhanced the deterioration of Keats's health and add fuel to his untimely death by Tuberculosis in Rome-"**envy and calumny and hate and pain**". But now Keats is beyond the "viperous murderer" or critic's venomous grip, he is now in the divine sphere where none can harm this pure and innocent soul.

He has outsoar'd the shadow of our night;
Envy and calumny and hate and pain,
And that unrest which men miscall delight,
Can touch him not and torture not again;
From the contagion of the world's slow stain
He is secure, and now can never mourn
A heart grown cold, a head grown gray in vain;
Nor, when the spirit's self has ceas'd to burn,
With sparkless ashes load an unlamented urn.

In this elegy Shelley welcomes the muse Urania, all the subject matters of Keats's eternal literary creations, his fellow poets and nature to weep for the great soul on his death and departure to the divine realm. Beauty and spring are unable to take the poet back into life. Then he urges them not to mourn his death as he is now in better condition. His soul has left the worldly existence and has attained the spiritual province. He will be greeted by the past legendary poets for his own poetic eminence and his enormous contribution in the Romantic poetry and in the English literature. He will definitely rest peace in there. Shelley himself anticipates his impending death in the last of this elegy.

- **In Memoriam A. H. H. OBIT MDCCCXXXIII: 27 (1850) :Alfred, Lord Tennyson**-this is an heart touching elegy written after the death of Tennyson's Cambridge friend, Arthur Henry Hallam's sudden death due to cerebral haemorrhage in 1833. This is a long elegiac narrative poem containing 2916 lines and 133 cantos written in iambic tetrameter with abba rhyming scheme. The poet here seeks wisdom from God and with heavy heart carries the burden of his grief and personal loss due to his friend's death.

I hold it true, whate'er befall;
I feel it, when I sorrow most;
'Tis better to have loved and lost
Than never to have loved at all.

The poet knows that his friend is now under God's custody but cannot tolerate the unbearable pain of his death as "all is dark where thou art not." Genuine grief cannot be expressed through mere words.

I sometimes hold it half a sin
To put in words the grief I feel;
For words, like Nature, half reveal
And half conceal the Soul within.

But, for the unquiet heart and brain,
A use in measured language lies;
The sad mechanic exercise,
Like dull narcotics, numbing pain.

Though it is futile to mourn the death "the fool of loss" but the near and dear ones cannot endure the pain of this heart rending loss. The death of his friend filled his world with an unspeakable emptiness. He hopes for Hallam's sudden return when sees the ship. The silence of the nature resonate the 'calmer grief' of the poet whose condition is like a widower. The grave of A.H.Hallam can only comfort his unrest mind. Here in this elegy there are allusions of Urania, the goddess of Astronomy and Melpomene, the goddess of elegy. The poet contemplates on Hallam's spirit in the afterlife is looking at him. He yearns for his companionship in spring and the summer. He eulogizes human beings' fortune to get a elevated status even in the afterlife in the divine presence of the almighty God.

- **Thyrsis: A Monody (1866): Matthew Arnold**-This is another great literary work of the English poetry written by the Victorian poet Matthew Arnold. This is a long poem containing 240 lines -the 24 ten- lines stanzas combining iambic pentameter and iambic trimeter in the sixth line with the constant abcba dede rhyming scheme of each stanza. This pastoral elegy follows the Classical Greek tradition where the Shepherd poet, Matthew Arnold "Corydon" laments the death of his friend and fellow poet Arthur Hugh Clough or Thyrsis of this poem. The name Thyrsis is derived from Virgil's seventh eclogue. The poem is set in the Oxford countryside in England. Arnold and Clough together have attended the Rugby School and the Oxford University. Clough was a brilliant student. This Victorian era was an era of conflict between Religious faith and scientific inventions. Industrialization of the Victorian era has created tremendous confusion and suspicion in spirituality and religious faith. There is a stark contrast between countryside beauty and simplicity with the urbane industrialization and artificiality. This issue has profoundly impacted on Arnold. The premature death of his close friend Arthur Hugh Clough in the year 1861 in Florence has shaken his existence in this situation more intensely. Both these bosom friends have lived happily for many years. They have intense love and admiration for each other. They have had many precious memories together. The time and situation in the Victorian society have transformed so much that the places are hard to recognize.

How changed is here each spot man makes or fills!
In the two Hinkseys nothing keeps the same;
The village street its haunted mansion lacks,
And from the sign is gone Sibylla's name,
And from the roofs the twisted chimney-stacks—
Are ye too changed, ye hills?
See, 'tis no foot of unfamiliar men
To-night from Oxford up your pathway strays!
Here came I often, often, in old days—
Thyrsis and I; we still had Thyrsis then.

Here is a mention of the Scholar Gypsy who will return only after his completion of the search of truth. The single old elm tree is connected with the Scholar Gypsy. The elegy is a journey of quest, the unending search for Truth. The Scholar Gypsy is devoted to explore the truth and the old elm tree is connected with him. If the tree is found then the Scholar is alive and he will return after his successful pursuit but if the tree cannot be found every endeavor will be futile. The poet here frantically searches the nostalgic tree for the glorious revelation of the truth.

That single elm-tree bright
Against the west—I miss it! is it gone?
We prized it dearly; while it stood, we said,
Our friend, the Gipsy-Scholar, was not dead;
While the tree lived, he in these fields lived on.

Here the poet accuses A.H. Clough for his own death. He constantly feels the pangs of abandonment and betrayal by his most favorite friend and intellectual companion Thyrsis. Arnold's own existence becomes miserable in England amidst the massive transformation of the situation, society, economy, surrounding perspectives and mostly in the belief system. He finds difficulty to cope with the changing world of so much spiritual crisis and it is most uncomfortable for him to live in this new world without his confidant. He becomes agitated when he does not fond the elm tree who is the witness of their friendship and a constant witness of the changing time. If the tree is noticed the truth will reveal otherwise the poet will be completely disenchanted with life and frustration will devour him. Finally the appearance of the elm tree is like the appearance of Truth itself. The presence of the elm tree suggests that the quest or journey for the Truth is not in vain. Something is constant in the flux of life amidst the changing flow of time. The poet should not blame Clough for his premature death and their friendship is as constant as the steadfast presence of the elm tree.

Theoretical Approaches:

Elegy is a ritualistic and social way to perform lamentation over the loss.

Fundamental theory of elegy by Peter M. Sack- Elegiac form has gone through several transformations from the Old age to the modern era. Elegy is a literary practice of mourning the dead-expressing the excruciating agony, praising the deceased person and his unique characteristics, and finally accepting the truth and prays for the peaceful afterlife of the deceased person.

Anti-elegy - This is a modern concept of Elegiac poetry propounded by Jahan Ramazani. It depicts that modern elegy has refused to console; it is fragmented and has no closure. It does not provide a definite consolation or acceptance of the agony. The pain is unresolved here and resistance to accept the crude reality.

Psychological aspect- Sigmund Freud differentiates between mourning and melancholia. Mourning lightens the burden of agony of the bereaved person therefore gradually detaching him emotionally from the loss and accepting the reality whereas melancholy enhances the burden of agony by internalizing it.

Archetypal Criticism of Northop Frye: Mythical patterns originated from the collective consciousness are used recurrently in the elegies. Universal patterns, motifs, symbols and archetypes are used time and again in the elegies.

Ecocriticism- The pastoral setting of the elegies, the rural countryside setting of Gray's elegy express that in the extreme pain of the human beings natural world comes for their solace and recreation. The bereaved hearts get comfort in the lap of the Mother Nature.

Conclusion: Elegy is a significant genre of literature which connects human beings universally. The feeling of loss of the dearest one does not remain mere personal agony of the poet but it finds global empathy through the lines of elegy. In the elegiac poetry the poet expresses his profound sorrow, recalls the precious memories with the deceased person, eulogizes his exclusive qualities and finally through sharing his intense feelings with the readers he becomes able to accept the universal law of nature and mortality. Anti-elegy on the other hand disagrees to accept the bitter truth of parting from the dear ones perpetually; it is willing to cherish the unresolved pain. The natural and pastoral setting of elegy is soothing and very near to the heart. Sorrow when shared with other people it loses its heavy burden likewise when elegy shares its grief to its readers the excruciating pain reduces its unfathomable heartache. Elegy is truly a marvelous invention of Literature which unites all the human beings emotionally and empathetically across the globe.

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